

Short Letters

Evaluation of the Wastewater at University of Technology

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Sewage water resulting from human vital activities and daily water use as well as from the quantities of waste resulting from industrial consumption and others that reach drinking water sources is one of the most important environmental problems to which humans are constantly exposed. The research aimed to study and analyze heavy water resulting from the buildings of scientific departments, research centers and laboratories at the University of Technology in Baghdad, as this study represents the chemical properties and heavy metals and the extent of their impact on the quality of the resulting water, analyze it, and find appropriate ways to treat and improve it. In this study, samples were taken from the heavy water produced at the University of Technology in Baghdad and from multiple drainage points spread throughout the university for separate periods of time and under different temperatures for the purpose of determining the extent of its effect on the chemical properties and heavy elements present in the wastewater. Examining and determining the quantity and percentage of heavy metal elements in water samples, including (Cd, Cr, Ni, Fe, Cu, Pb, Zn) The chemical properties of these samples were examined and determined, including (EC, pH, DO, Ca. TDS, Sal.) and compared with the international standard for the quantities and percentages of these properties. Appropriate methods were proposed to improve the quality and type of wastewater resulting from laboratories, Scientific centers and departments at the University of Technology.